

Online Energy Management Strategy of Fuel Cell Hybrid Electric Vehicles Based on Rule Learning

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Abstract: In this paper, a rule learning based energy management strategy is proposed to achieve preferable energy consumption economy for fuel cell hybrid electric vehicles. Firstly, the optimal control sequence of fuel cell power and the state of charge trajectory of lithium-ion battery pack during driving are derived offline by the Pontryagin's minimum principle. Next, the K-means algorithm is employed to hierarchically cluster the optimal solution into the simplified data set. Then, the repeated incremental pruning to produce error reduction algorithm, as a propositional rule learning strategy, is leveraged to learn and classify the underlying rules. Finally, the multiple linear regression algorithm is applied to fit the abstracted parameters of generated rule set. Simulation results highlight that the proposed strategy can achieve more than 95% savings of energy consumption economy, solved by Pontryagin's minimum principle, with less calculation intensity and without dependence on prior driving conditions, thereby manifesting the feasibility of online application.

Key words: Fuel cell hybrid electric vehicle, energy management strategy, hierarchical clustering, rule learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, fuel cell hybrid electric vehicles (FCHEVs), which are powered by fuel cells and energy storage systems (usually lithium-ion batteries), represent an important development direction of automotive industry. The hybrid powertrain of FCHEVs can compensate constraints of low power variation rates of fuel cells, and thus potentially prolongs lifespan of fuel cells and further improves the operation economy, compared with pure fuel cell vehicles [1, 2]. However, existence of two energy sources inside the FCHEV leads to the challenge of energy distribution between fuel cell and batteries that needs to be properly tackled. As such, effective design of energy management strategies (EMSs) becomes critical for improving the vehicle operation economy and prolonging lifetime of fuel cells [3, 4].

According to operation manners, EMSs of FCHEVs can be mainly divided into two classes, offline and online. Usually, the offline EMS is able to attain global optimal optimization under the different constraints. However, the price to be paid is to acquire the driving condition in advance. Certainly, it is impractical to apply in real operation and yet can be regarded as benchmarks for evaluating performances of online strategies [5]. Dynamic programming (DP) [6, 7], Pontryagin's minimum principle (PMP) [8, 9], and quadratic programming (QP) [10], as typical offline strategy representatives, have been widely employed to find global optimal solutions when the driving conditions are known [11-14]. In [15], a multi-dimensional DP is introduced to achieve optimal power distribution of the FCHEV for minimization of hydrogen consumption when driving information is acquired. In [16], main components matching of the FCHEV powertrain is researched to analyze influences on the multi-objective optimization incorporating fuel economy and system durability. By simplifying the energy management problem into a linear model, Ref. [17] proposes an offline optimal energy distribution method for FCHEVs with a form of combinatorial optimization.

On the other hand, online EMSs are widely adopted by production vehicles, and can be mainly classified into three categories. 1) The first type is to optimize the related controlling parameters offline and subsequently to apply them online, such as fuzzy logic (FL) strategies [14]; 2) the second class is the online strategy with the combination of global optimization principle, such as MPC and typical equivalent consumption minimization strategies (ECMSs) [18]; and 3) the last one is the EMS based on machine learning algorithms, such as neural network (NN) and supported vector machine (SVM) based strategies [19]. Currently, the first type of online EMSs has been widely investigated by academia. In [20], the hydrogen consumption is optimized by PMP with the known driving conditions, and two robust controllers are created based on offline optimization results, thereby achieving online power allocation. In [21], the hydrogen consumption of fuel cell and battery lifespan in a FCHEV are simultaneously optimized by DP. On this basis, the soft-run strategy is introduced to achieve the configured multi-objective optimization online. In [22], an auto-regressive moving average (ARMA) regulator is developed based on the optimal energy consumption of FCHEVs solved by PMP. In [23], to meet the power demand and meanwhile endeavor to prolong the fuel cell lifespan, genetic algorithm (GA) is firstly harnessed to regulate all the correlated parameters to achieve the optimal energy distribution in deterministic driving cycles, and then a FL based control strategy is built for online implementation. In [24], on the basis of comprehensive analysis of the global optimization results, the FL based EMS is constructed for real-time application in FCHEVs.

In addition, real-time EMSs with incorporation of global optimization solutions, referred to as the second types, have also been widely studied. Ref. [25] introduces a real-time optimal control strategy for FCHEVs by merging the Markov chain and PMP. In [26], an adaptive PMP based strategy is raised to allocate the power between the fuel cell and battery, and meanwhile the adaptive recursive least square algorithm is loaded to search the optimal efficiency point of the proton exchange membrane fuel cell (PEMFC). In [27], with the help of offline optimization solved by PMP, a uniform EMS for real-time application is put forward that considers the multi-objective optimization including reduction of fuel consumption and extension of battery lifespan. In [28], a two-step EMS is adopted to optimally allocate the energy of FCHEV. Firstly, the hysteresis based EMS is employed to online identify parameter variations of the semi-empirical model of PEMFCs and to update the model dynamically, and finally PMP is applied to resolve the power allocation. In [29], an extremum seeking controller (ESC) is adopted to enable the fuel cell system (FCS) working in the high efficiency area, thereby reducing the hydrogen consumption dramatically. Simultaneously, state of charge (SOC) of the battery is exploited as the input of penalty function to prevent overcharge and over-discharge. In [30], an online EMS based on the deterministic DP (DDP) is proposed for daily operation optimization on a settled route. In [31-33], a real-time optimization strategy based on the global extremum seeking (GES) algorithm is constructed to attain multi-mode surface optimization. In [34], an EMS based on the dynamic factor regulation is proposed for the FCHEV, and it can improve the operating efficiency of vehicle without reliance on knowing driving conditions. Ref. [35] introduces an ECMS for FCHEVs based on the sequential QP. In [36], an online adaptive PMP based EMS is introduced to optimize the static model of fuel cell and battery, and effectiveness of the EMS is verified by a hardware-in-loop (HIL) experimental setup.

With the progressive development of calculation capability of modern computer systems, EMSs based on machine learning have been widely spurred [37]. The earliest machine learning solutions are based on NNs, such as the back propagation NN (BPNN), and learning vector quantization (LVQ) [38]. In [39], the NN, optimized by the gradient descent method, is leveraged to train the optimal power distribution under the standard driving cycles; whereby an online EMS is formulated with adaption to different driving conditions. Currently, EMSs based on reinforcement learning (RL) have been widely researched. In [40], a real-time EMS is proposed based on the speedy Q-learning algorithm. In [41], an EMS based on deep Q learning (DQL) is constructed to solve the so-called curse of dimensionality incurred by a variety of discrete state variables existing in the traditional Q learning. In [42], a real-time RL based EMS is proposed to optimally distribute the power between

the battery and super capacitor. Similarly, in [43], the RL algorithm is implemented to effectively distribute the power between the engine and battery.

As a branch of machine learning, rule learning is based on strict mathematical logic and can update inner rules by importing new domain knowledge during learning process. Nowadays, rule learning has been widely applied in industry, and simulation and experimental results manifest its strong capability of learning and pre-judgement in view of unforeseen cases [44, 45]. In [46], the repeated incremental pruning to produce error reduction (RIPPER) algorithm, as a class of rule learning, is firstly proposed to generate the rule set with satisfactory prediction results. In [47], the ant colony optimization algorithm is proposed to solve the problem of coverage among rules caused by the RIPPER algorithm. In [48], the RIPPER algorithm is applied in multiclass classification to improve the identification precision. In [49], a complexity-based parallel rule learning (CPRL) is proposed to reduce the impact of learning order for the RIPPER algorithm, and on this basis, GA is harnessed to sort the rule order. In [50], the PRISM algorithm based on rule learning is firstly introduced to effectively replicate sub-trees. However, the model trained by the algorithm exhibits higher complexity. As such, in [51], a competitive target class (CTC) algorithm based on PRISM is proposed, which can reduce the risk of over-fitting and the complexity of model. Inspired by the discussed applications intuitively, the rule learning based strategy should be able to excavate hidden rules existing in energy management of FCHEVs. Additionally, similar to be applied in other fields, the rule learning-based strategy can cast off the dependence of prior knowledge of trip information and update the rule set by means of self-learning. Thus, it can overcome the restrictions of formulating rules with much effort existing in conventional rule-based EMSs and of acquiring prior driving information, that is critical for global optimization based EMSs. To the best of authors' knowledge, it has been not reported in publications with respect to the rule learning principle applied in EMS, and therefore becomes the main motivation of this study. To apply the rule learning principle, the PMP algorithm is called firstly to acquire the optimal control sequence and state trajectories based on the deterministic driving cycle. On this basis, the K-means algorithm is adopted to simplify the optimal data set and eliminate the redundant data. Then, the improved RIPPER algorithm is harnessed to extract the rules from the simplified data set, and subsequently the multiple linear regression manipulation is employed to identify the parameters of learned rules. Simulation results manifest that the proposed EMS based on rule learning can reach more than 95% energy consumption economy of the PMP based offline solution with less computation intensity and without dependence on prior driving conditions, demonstrating the feasibility of online implementation. The main

contributions of this study are attributed to the following two aspects: 1) an EMS based on rule learning is proposed, and it can improve the energy consumption economy with the capability of real-time application; and 2) a hierarchical clustering method is devised to effectively simplify the data set and solve the problem of over-fitting during the learning process.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. In Section II, the powertrain of the studied FCHEV is modeled and the corresponding mathematical analysis is conducted. In Section III, the optimal EMS based on PMP is introduced. The real-time EMS based on the rule learning is elaborated in Section IV. Simulation validation is performed in Section V, followed by the main conclusions drawn in Section VI.

II. MODELING OF THE STUDIED FCHEV

A. FCHEV Model

As shown in Fig. 1 (a), the powertrain topology of studied FCHEV is similar to that of the conventional hybrid electric vehicles (HEVs), in which the power sources are connected to wheels through an electric motor. The powertrain of FCHEV mainly consists of the fuel cell, power battery, DC/DC converter, DC/AC inverter and motor. The simulation model is sketched in Fig. 1 (b), mainly including the fuel cell sub-model, energy management system, lithium-ion battery sub-model, motor and vehicle model. In this study, the PEMFC is considered as the primary energy source for supplying the steady driving power and is electrically connected to the DC power bus through a unidirectional DC/DC converter. As the main energy storage source, the lithium-ion battery pack directly connects to the DC bus to maintain the voltage stable. Additionally, it can supply extra energy when the vehicle accelerates and absorb regenerative energy when braking. The basic parameters of the vehicle are listed in Table I.

Fig. 1. The powertrain system of FCHEVs. (a) The powertrain system of FCHEVs; (b) The simulation model of powertrain.

The longitudinal dynamics equation of vehicle, as introduced in [52], can be formulated as:

$$F_i = mgf \cos \alpha + \frac{1}{2} C_D A \rho V^2(t) + G \sin \alpha + \delta m \frac{dV}{dt} \quad (1)$$

where F_i is the driving force of the vehicle, m denotes the vehicle mass, g represents gravitational acceleration, and f expresses the rolling resistance coefficient. α denotes slope of the road, C_D means the windward resistance coefficient, A represents the windward area, ρ is air density, $V(t)$ represents the vehicle speed, and δ denotes the weight coefficient of rotating mass. In this study, we assume that the driving cycles are with negligible road gradient and sufficient road adhesion coefficients. As such, the balance equation between the driving force and resistance of the vehicle can be expressed as:

$$F_i = mgf + \frac{1}{2} C_D \rho V^2(t) + \delta m \frac{dV}{dt} \quad (2)$$

In addition, the required power can be calculated as:

$$P_{load}(t) = V(t) \times \left(mgf + \frac{1}{2} C_D \rho V^2(t) + \delta m \frac{dV}{dt} \right) \quad (3)$$

The power demand of whole vehicle from the power source can be formulated as:

$$P_{re}(t) = \frac{P_{load}(t)}{\eta_{DC/AC} \cdot \eta_{motor}} \quad (4)$$

where $\eta_{DC/AC}$ and η_{motor} represent the efficiency of DC/AC converter and motor, respectively. Furthermore, we can easily attain:

$$P_{re} = P_{fc} + P_{bat} \quad (5)$$

where P_{fc} represents the output power of the fuel cell, and P_{bat} denotes the battery power.

Table I Basic parameters of FCHEV

Characteristic	Value
Mass	1700kg
Frontal projected area	2.59m ²
Air drag coefficient	0.35
Air density	1.29
Roll resistance coefficient	0.014

B. Fuel Cell System Model

The mathematical model of fuel cell can be derived according to physical laws of operation and related conditions. This study considers the static model of a PEMFC system as the research object. By assuming that the ambient temperature, humidity, and gas pressure of fuel cells are all in steady state, the system can provide

a specific power and consume a set amount of hydrogen. According to calibration results conducted on the test bench, the relationship between the power output and efficiency of PEMFC is plotted in Fig. 2. When the fuel cell operates in a low power mode, the power efficiency is low as the auxiliary system of fuel cell stack consumes most of the power and meanwhile maintains normal function of the entire system; whereas the power efficiency is also reduced in high load power mode due to physical restrictions of the fuel cell stack.

Fig. 2. Fuel cell model. (a) The net power and efficiency map of fuel cell model; (b) The relationship between hydrogen consumption rate and fuel cell output power.

The relationship between the hydrogen consumption rate and output power can be calculated as:

$$\dot{m}_{H_2} = \frac{P_{fc}}{\eta_{fc} \times LHV} \quad (6)$$

where \dot{m}_{H_2} , P_{fc} and η_{fc} denote the hydrogen consumption rate, output power, and efficiency of the full cell system, respectively; and LHV expresses its lower heat value and equals $120MJ / Kg$ in this study. The hydrogen consumption rate of fuel cell can be calculated according to (6), and the relationship between the hydrogen consumption rate and output power is shown in Fig. 2 (b). The hydrogen consumption rate is fitted by a fourth-order polynomial equation, expressed in (7), enabling that the loop check of the interpolation function can be reduced, thus shortening the calculation time. Table II shows the fitting parameters in (7).

$$\dot{m}_{H_2} = b_1 \times P_{fc}^4 + b_2 \times P_{fc}^3 + b_3 \times P_{fc}^2 + b_4 \times P_{fc} + b_5 \quad (7)$$

Table II The fitting parameters of hydrogen consumption

Fitting Parameters	Value
b_1	1.526×10^{-7}
b_2	-1.577×10^{-5}
b_3	0.0004387
b_4	0.009941
b_5	0.02112

C. Lithium-ion Battery Model

In this paper, a power lithium-ion battery with the capacity of 5 Ah and the rated voltage of 300 V is selected as the auxiliary energy source. Previous studies have shown that the R -int model can effectively reflect the battery electrical performance with moderate calculation labor [53, 54]. As shown in Fig. 3 (a), this model consists of an open circuit voltage (OCV) source and an equivalent series connected internal resistor. Consequently, the output power P_b can be calculated and the current I_b can be inversely solved, as:

$$\begin{cases} P_b(SOC) = E(SOC) \times I_b - I_b^2 \times R(SOC) \\ I_b = \frac{E(SOC) - \sqrt{E^2(SOC) - 4 \times R(SOC) \times P_b(SOC)}}{2 \times R(SOC)} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where E indicates the open circuit voltage of the battery, and R is the internal resistance of the battery. The built EMS needs to consider the battery SOC and in this study the coulomb counting method is employed, as:

$$SOC(t) = SOC_{to} - \frac{\int_{to}^t I_b dt}{3600Q} \quad (9)$$

where $SOC(t)$ represents the SOC value at time t , SOC_{to} denotes the initial SOC value of battery, and Q means the battery rated capacity.

The relationship between the internal resistance and SOC under the charge and discharge conditions and different temperatures is shown in Fig. 3 (b). As can be clearly seen, when SOC ranges from 0.25 to 1, the internal resistance basically keeps at around 0.6 ohm. The relationship between OCV and SOC at different temperatures is shown in Fig. 3 (c). It can be observed that the OCV is stable at around 300 V when SOC increases from 0.3 to 0.8. For ease of simplifying the problem, previous studies have adopted that the main parameters of battery remain unchanged when SOC locates in the middle range [55] and this study also accepts this simplification. The relevant parameters of battery are shown in Table III.

Fig. 3. Lithium-ion battery. (a) Battery liner model; (b) The relationship between resistance and SOC; (c) the relationship between open voltage and SOC.

Table III Battery parameters

Battery Parameters	Values
Rated output voltage	300 V
Internal resistance	0.6 Ω
Energy	1.5 Kwh
SOC range	0.3 to 0.8
Charge-discharge maximum rate	12 C

III. ENERGY MANAGEMENT STRATEGY BASED ON PMP FOR FCHEV

Previous studies have highlighted effectiveness of PMP when searching the global optimal solution for PHEVs [9, 56], and therefore in this study, PMP is employed to optimize the output power sequence of fuel cell in determined driving conditions, and achieve the optimal power distribution between two energy sources with the target of minimizing the hydrogen consumption.

A. Optimization of Energy Management for FCHEV

Actually, the optimization objective of energy management is a nonlinear sequential optimization problem in finite duration. The detailed target is to minimize the hydrogen consumption in a determined interval $[t_0, t_f]$. To attain it, the fuel cell power and battery SOC are considered as the control variable $u(t)$ and state variable $x(t)$, respectively. The overall energy consumption consists of the hydrogen consumption and electric energy loss. When evaluating the fuel economy, it is necessary to ensure that the final SOC should be kept the same with the initial value. If the difference between the initial and terminal SOC exists, it should be translated to the equivalent hydrogen consumption. In this study, the equivalent hydrogen consumption arisen by the SOC difference is calculated by the equivalent heat value [57], as:

$$m_{H_2, bat} = \begin{cases} \frac{U_{bat_avg} (SOC(t_f) - SOC(t_0)) Q \eta_{batdis_avg}}{\eta_{DC/DC} \eta_{fc_avg} LHV}, & SOC(t_f) - SOC(t_0) > 0 \\ \frac{U_{bat_avg} (SOC(t_f) - SOC(t_0))}{\eta_{DC/DC} \eta_{batchr_avg} \eta_{fc_avg} LHV}, & SOC(t_f) - SOC(t_0) < 0 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

where $m_{H_2,bat}$ is the equivalent hydrogen consumption of the battery; U_{bat_avg} denotes the battery average voltage; $\eta_{DC/DC}$ expresses average efficiency of the DC/DC converter, η_{batchr_avg} and η_{batdis_avg} are the average discharge and charge efficiency, respectively; and η_{fc_avg} represents the fuel cell average efficiency. By summing the polynomial model in (7) of calculating the hydrogen consumption and the equivalent hydrogen consumption incurred by the battery [58], the cost function can be formulated as:

$$J = \Phi(SOC(t_f), t_f) + \int_{t_0}^{t_f} \dot{m}_{H_2}(P_{fc}(t), t) dt \quad (11)$$

$$\Phi(SOC(t_f), t_f) = \begin{cases} m_{H_2,bat}, & \text{if the SOC difference meets constraint} \\ 10000, & \text{if the SOC difference does not meet constraint} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

where $\Phi(SOC(t_f), t_f)$ represents the penalty function for the terminal state variable. Here, the constraint means the SOC difference should be limited with 0.005. Now, the objective of EMS turns to minimization of the cost function, as:

$$\min J(SOC, P_{fc}) = \min \left\{ \Phi(SOC(t_f), t_f) + \int_{t_0}^{t_f} \dot{m}_{H_2}(P_{fc}(t), t) dt \right\} \quad (13)$$

In addition, the state equation can be expressed as:

$$\dot{SOC}(t) = -\frac{1}{3600Q} \times \frac{E(SOC) - \sqrt{E^2(SOC) - 4 \times R(SOC) \times P_b(t)}}{2 \times R(SOC)} \quad (14)$$

$$P_b(t) = P_{re}(t) - P_{fc}(t) \quad (15)$$

where P_b is the battery power, and P_{re} expresses the power demand of motor (kW). The constraints for state variables are mainly consists of three parts: 1) the initial and ending SOC; 2) the battery current thresholds; and 3) the optimal operation performance of battery. The reasons are detailed as follows. Firstly, since the fuel cell is the main power source and the battery is only regarded as the auxiliary energy source, it should be constrained within a reasonable range. Secondly, the battery lifespan is affected by the charge and discharge current, and the larger the value, the faster the battery degradation will be [59]. As such, the current thresholds of battery should be constrained for ensuring its lifetime. Thirdly, the range of SOC variation should be constrained. In summary, all the related constraints in terms of SOC can be expressed as:

$$\begin{cases} SoC(t_0) = 0.6 \\ |SoC(t_f) - SoC(t_0)| \leq 0.005 \\ C - rate(t) \leq 8C \\ SoC_{min} \leq SoC(t) \leq SoC_{max} \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

where $SoC_{min}=0.3$ and $SoC_{max}=0.8$. The constraints of battery power can be written as:

$$\begin{cases} P_b(t) = P_{req}(t) - P_{fc}(t) \\ P_{bmin} \leq P_b(t) \leq P_{bmax} \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

where P_{bmin} and P_{bmax} denote the battery minimum and maximum output power, respectively. In addition, the fuel cell lifetime is directly related to the driving conditions, including the load variation, on/off times, idle time and peak power load [60]. Therefore, the following constraints for the fuel cell can be imposed, as:

$$\begin{cases} P_{fc_min} \leq P_{fc}(t) \leq P_{fc_max} \\ |\Delta P_{fc}(t)| \leq 5KW \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

where $P_{fc_min}=0$, $P_{fc_max}=62 kW$, and $|\Delta P_{fc}(t)|$ denotes the power difference of the fuel cell before and after each step.

B. Solution of Offline Optimal EMS

It is necessary to define the Hamilton function when the PMP is applied to solve the optimal control, as:

$$H(SOC, P_{fc}, \lambda, t) = \dot{m}_{H_2}(P_{fc}, t) + \lambda(t) \dot{SOC}(t) \quad (19)$$

where $\lambda(t)$, denoting the co-state, represents the equivalent consumption parameter. Based on PMP, the fuel cell output power sequence can be found to minimize the Hamilton function during the entire driving cycle, and the solution can be expressed as:

$$P_{fc}^* = \operatorname{argmin} H(t, \dot{SOC}^*(t), \lambda^*(t)) \quad (20)$$

Moreover, the necessary conditions of the PMP-based optimal control can be constructed, as:

$$\begin{cases} H(\dot{SOC}^*(t), P_{fc}^*, \lambda^*(t), t) \leq H(\dot{SOC}(t), P_{fc}(t), \lambda(t), t) \\ \dot{SOC}^*(t) = \frac{\partial H}{\partial \lambda^*(t)} \\ \dot{\lambda}^*(t) = -\frac{\partial H}{\partial SOC(t)} \\ \lambda(t_f) = \text{constant} \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

where

$$\begin{cases} \dot{SOC}^*(t) = -\frac{I_b^*(t)}{3600Q} \\ I_b^*(t) = \frac{E(SOC) - \sqrt{E^2(SOC) - 4 \times R(SOC) \times P_b(t)}}{2 \times R(SOC)} \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

$$\dot{\lambda}^*(t) = \frac{\lambda^*(t)}{3600Q} \times \left(\frac{\partial I_b^*(t)}{\partial R(t)} \times \frac{dR(SOC)}{dSOC} + \frac{\partial I_b^*(t)}{\partial E(t)} \times \frac{dE(SOC)}{dSOC} \right) \quad (23)$$

According to the previous analysis, the SOC value is restricted within a certain range, making both the open circuit voltage E and internal resistance R be constant and independent of SOC. Thus, we can attain:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dE(SOC)}{dSOC} = 0 \\ \frac{dR(SOC)}{dSOC} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

As such, we can attain that $\dot{\lambda}^*(t)$ equals zero, which means $\lambda(t)$ is a constant, as:

$$\lambda(t) = \lambda(t_f) = \lambda(t_0) = constant \quad (25)$$

Given the driving condition and constraints, the iterative search method is harnessed to solve the co-state value. The detailed steps of determining λ are illustrated as follows:

- (1) Assign a random initial value to the co-state and discretize the fuel cell power.
- (2) Combine the road power demand and Hamilton function, and solve the optimal P_{fc}^* at this moment.
- (3) Repeat steps (1) to (2) until the last moment.
- (4) Evaluate the terminal SOC value and compare it with the initial SOC value. If the deviation meets the constraint, the value assigned in step (1) is selected as the co-state value. Otherwise, repeat steps (1) to (3) until reaching the termination condition.

In this study, a blended driving cycle consisting of NEDC, UDDS, LA92, HWFET and WVUSUB cycles is built as the fundamental driving cycle for the rule training dataset. The built driving cycle involves the congested, suburban and high speed driving conditions. The optimal control variable sequence of the blended driving cycle is solved by PMP, and the velocity trajectory is shown in Fig. 4 (a). The corresponding optimal SOC trajectory and hydrogen consumption based on PMP are shown in Figs. 4 (b) and (c), respectively. As can be seen, when the power demand is relatively large, e.g., from 1000 s to 2000 s, the power demand is supplied by both sources, leading to dramatic decline of SOC. Furthermore, the hydrogen consumption increases sharply, as shown in Fig. 4 (c). On the contrary, when the power demand is lower, both variation rates of SOC and

hydrogen consumption are relatively flat, suggesting that the distribution of power sources can be reasonably allocated by the PMP.

Fig. 4. The blended driving cycle simulation results. (a) Speed curve of the blended driving cycle; (b) Optimal SOC trajectory; (c) Hydrogen consumption curve.

In the next step, the rule learning is conducted by extracting the imbedded laws hidden in the optimal solution.

IV. ENERGY MANAGEMENT STRATEGY BASED ON RULE LEARNING

The essence of EMS based on rule learning is to excavate the implicit laws hidden in the existing optimal data set, and then to define attributes and categories of rules. On the basis of the searched optimal solution, the optimal data set is constructed, and the parameters that can reflect the power demand are selected as the attributes in the optimal data set, including the velocity, acceleration and SOC. The optimization fuel cell power sequence is regarded as the output category of optimal data set. The EMS block diagram based on rule learning is shown in Fig. 5. As can be observed, to achieve finding the rules, three cascaded tasks are successively conducted, including the offline optimization, simplification of optimal data, and rule learning.

Fig. 5. Schematic framework of the rule learning EMS.

A Simplification of the Optimal Data Set

The number of rules in the database is the same as time steps of the built blended cycle. No doubt, larger amount of number and dataset will lead to more complexity during the rule learning process. Particularly, it will become easier to fall into over-fitting if the learning process is conducted point-by-point. To reduce computation labor and avoid over-fitting, it is indispensable to simplify the optimal data set. In this study, the K-means algorithm is employed to cluster the optimal data set in an iterative optimization manner, thus the cluster set can be updated, and meanwhile the mean vector of each cluster is summed. If the clustering result remains unchanged after the iterative update, the cluster is completed [61, 62]. To attain more accurate classification data, the data set is hierarchically clustered in this study. Firstly, the output power of fuel cell in the data set is classified, and then the corresponding attribution to each cluster is found, and sequentially the velocity, acceleration and SOC of each cluster is classified. The specific training process of each cluster is detailed in Fig. 6. Note that the reason of setting the clustering order is explained as follows: 1) P_{fc} is the control variable which should be firstly categorized; 2) V , a and SOC are state inputs of the vehicle, and the first two variables can directly influence the power demand, and the last one can take an indirect effect in driving ability of vehicle incurred by the auxiliary power source. Therefore, V and a should be clustered with higher priority.

According to the energy supply capability, the fuel cell output power is classified into three categories, and the speed is divided into four categories according to characteristics of driving conditions, and the acceleration is categorized into four classes in terms of the driving trend, and the SOC is divided into three types in the light of supplied power. In this paper, after finishing clustering, the median is selected to find the centralized location of each cluster for finally confirming each cluster's category.

Fig. 6. The hierarchical clustering operation.

B Rule Learning Based Optimal Data Set

The main target of rule learning is to study the training data set, endeavoring to cover all the samples and generating the effective rule set [63]. In this study, an improved RIPPER algorithm is leveraged to extract the rules, sort all of them in line with the priority principle and guarantee effectiveness of the found rules. During the learning process, the beam search technique is adopted to evaluate pros and cons of rules. The attribute value of rules with highest accuracy will be kept in each learning process. To solve the problem that the selected rule can easily fall into local optimum, three classes of rules are simultaneously learned, and the data set is updated together until no new rules can be generated. The steps based on the improved RIPPER algorithm are shown in Table IV. According to the elaborated rule learning steps, a total of twenty rules are built with a fixed order, as detailed in Table V, and a default rule is established to deal the uncovered data. As can be seen, the rules contain all the classes of speed, acceleration and SOC. The corresponding thresholds with respect to rules is listed in Table VI. In summary, the learned twenty rules are divided into four classes in terms of the priority sequence. According to the priority and defined rules, the final power demand of fuel cell can be thus determined.

Table IV Improved RIPPER Algorithm

1.	Input Optimal Data set
2.	For i=1: 3
3.	Rules (i) =Cover Data
4.	$R' = R_1 \cup R_2 \cup R_3$
5.	End
6.	Delete sub data set covered by R'
7.	Update the Data set
8.	Repeat
9.	$R = R' \cup R''$
10.	Until all the data is covered
11.	Output R

Table V Rules Set

	Speed	Acceleration	SOC	Fuel cell power	Priority
1	Low speed	Smooth acceleration	/	Pfc_output1	1 st priority
2	Medium Speed	Smooth acceleration	/	Pfc_output2	1 st priority
3	High Speed	/	/	Pfc_output3	1 st priority
4	Low Speed	Smooth deceleration	/	Pfc_output4	1 st priority
5	Medium Speed	Smooth deceleration	/	Pfc_output5	1 st priority
6	Low speed	Urgent acceleration	Low	Pfc_output6	2 nd priority
7	Fairly high speed	Urgent deceleration	/	Pfc_output7	2 nd priority
8	Medium Speed	/	/	Pfc_output8	2 nd priority
9	/	Urgent acceleration	High	Pfc_output9	3 rd priority
10	Low speed	/	Low	Pfc_output10	3 rd priority
11	/	Urgent deceleration	Low	Pfc_output11	3 rd priority
12	Low speed	Urgent acceleration	Medium	Pfc_output12	4 th priority
13	Fairly high speed	Smooth acceleration	Medium	Pfc_output13	4 th priority
14	Fairly high speed	Smooth deceleration	Low	Pfc_output14	4 th priority
15	Fairly high speed	Smooth deceleration	Medium	Pfc_output15	4 th priority
16	Fairly high speed	Smooth deceleration	High	Pfc_output16	4 th priority
17	Fairly high speed	Smooth acceleration	Low	Pfc_output17	4 th priority
18	Low speed	Urgent deceleration	Medium	Pfc_output18	4 th priority
19	Low speed	Urgent deceleration	High	Pfc_output19	4 th priority
20	Fairly high speed	Smooth acceleration	High	Pfc_output20	4 th priority

Table VI Literal information

Variables	Value range	Unit
Classification		
Low speed	[0, 11.1)	m/s
Medium speed	[11.1, 16.7)	m/s
Fairly high speed	[16.7, 25)	m/s
High speed	[25, +∞)	m/s
Urgent deceleration	(-∞, -0.9]	m/s ²
Smooth deceleration	(-0.9, 0)	m/s ²
Smooth acceleration	[0, 0.7)	m/s ²
Urgent acceleration	[0.7, +∞)	m/s ²
Low SOC	[0.3, 0.45)	
Medium SOC	[0.45, 0.6)	
High SOC	[0.6, 1]	

C Rule Learning-Based Multiple Linear Regression Model

Actually, each rule in the whole set learned from the offline optimal solution can be regarded as an optimal data set. Through the hypothesis test analysis, we can find that the attributes in the rules are strongly related to the output power of fuel cell. To better describe the relationship, multiple linear regression models are employed to fit the data of each rule, as:

$$Y = \theta_0 + \theta_1 x_1 + \theta_2 x_2 + \dots + \theta_m x_m \quad (26)$$

where Y denotes the fuel cell net power, x_m represents the attribute value corresponding to each rule, and $\theta_0, \theta_1, \dots, \theta_m$ are the regression coefficient. Since each rule is extracted according to multiple samples, equation (26) can be formulated in a matrix form, as:

$$Y = X\theta \quad (27)$$

and

$$\begin{cases} Y = [y_1 & y_2 & \cdots & y_n]^T \\ X = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & x_{11} & x_{12} & \cdots & x_{1m} \\ 1 & x_{21} & x_{22} & \cdots & x_{2m} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \cdots & \vdots \\ 1 & x_{n1} & x_{n2} & \cdots & x_{nm} \end{bmatrix}_{n \times m} \\ \theta = [\theta_0 & \theta_1 & \cdots & \theta_m]^T \end{cases} \quad (28)$$

where X represents the sample data for by the rule. Each row of X denotes the attribute value of samples covered by the rule. $n \times m$ indicates that the rule contains m attributes and n samples. In this paper, the normal equation is used to solve the regression coefficient [64], as:

$$\theta = (X^T X)^{-1} X^T Y \quad (29)$$

In addition, to validate whether the aforementioned fitting curves are optimal or not, the F-test and T-test are respectively performed to conduct the significance test of difference based on the learned regression model along with its regression coefficient, when the significance coefficient α equals 0.1. The calculation procedures of the F-test are detailed as:

$$\begin{cases} F = \frac{S_R^2 / m}{S_E^2 / (n - m - 1)} \\ S_E^2 = \sum_{i=1}^{i=n} (y_i - \hat{y})^2 \\ S_R^2 = \sum_{i=1}^{i=n} (\hat{y} - \bar{y})^2 \end{cases} \quad (30)$$

where y_i denotes the output power of the fuel cell solved by PMP, \hat{y} expresses the output power fitted by regression model, and \bar{y} represents the average fuel cell power optimized by PMP in this rule. Moreover, the calculation process of the T-test can be formulated as:

$$\begin{cases} T_i = \frac{\theta_i / c_{ii}}{S_E^2 / (n - m - 1)}, i = 1, 2, 3. \\ C = (X^T X)^{-1} \end{cases} \quad (31)$$

where c_{ii} is the element of matrix C .

In the next step, numerical simulations and related discussions are conducted to validate the effectiveness of proposed rule learning based EMS.

V. SIMULATION AND DISCUSSION

To verify the effectiveness of proposed EMS in this paper, the standard and real driving cycles are respectively simulated and analyzed. In this paper, all the simulations were conducted in Matlab/Simulink. PMP is also applied to find the offline optimal solution, which can be regarded as a benchmark to evaluate the performance of the proposed algorithm. To achieve the simulation with the offline PMP strategy and designed rule learning strategy, the following constraints are considered, as:

$$\begin{cases} P_{fc_min} \leq P_{fc}(t) \leq P_{fc_max} \\ SOC_{min} \leq SOC(t) \leq SOC_{max} \\ C-rate(t) \leq C_{constrain} \\ |\Delta P_{fc}(t)| \leq 5Kw \\ P_b(t) \leq P_{bmax} \end{cases} \quad (32)$$

It is necessary to note that when the output power of fuel cell is lower, the output power the battery may exceed its maximum value. In this case, the low power threshold of fuel cell should be ignored, and the fuel cell power should be increased to meet the power demand.

A Standard Driving Cycle Simulation and Analysis

The UDDS, HWFET, US06, UNIF06 and LA92 standard driving cycles, representing the urban, suburban, high speed and aggressive driving conditions, are selected to verify the effectiveness of proposed strategy. Firstly, the optimal co-state variables of each driving cycle are determined by PMP, and then the hydrogen consumption of the corresponding standard driving cycle is calculated considering the constraints. Then, the EMS based on rule learning is applied to each driving cycle, and the results are compared with that solved by PMP. The hydrogen consumption of each driving cycle is shown in Table VII. As can be found, the hydrogen consumption based on the proposed strategy only increases by 0.29%, 3.75%, 0.25%, 4.68%, and 2.1%, compared with the PMP optimization results in the standard driving cycles, proving the effectiveness of proposed method in optimizing the fuel economy performance.

Table VII Comparison of the hydrogen consumptions in five standard driving cycles.

	LA92	UDDS	UNIF01	HWFET	US06
Driving time (s)	1436	1370	1931	766	601
Maximum speed (m/s)	29.87	25.2	32.92	26.62	35.69
Average speed (m/s)	10.93	8.70	11.35	21.42	21.31
Hydrogen consumption based on PMP based (g)	118.99	68.62	175.43	119.53	144.48
Hydrogen consumption based on rule learning (g)	119.34	71.30	175.87	125.41	147.58
	(+0.29%)	(+3.75%)	(+0.25%)	(+4.68%)	(+2.1%)

Note: +: Increment

To further evaluate the performance of EMS based on the rule learning, we analyze the driving conditions, rule selection and power distribution in more detail. Obviously, when the LA92 cycle is simulated, the built algorithm can obtain the most similar hydrogen consumption, compared with PMP; and in contrast, when the HWFET cycle is tested, the hydrogen consumption based on the built algorithm shows the most increment in comparison with that of PMP. Fig. 7 shows the simulation results under the LA92 cycle. As can be seen from Fig. 7 (b), the LA92 cycle is mainly composed of low speed driving conditions and only a small part of high speed driving conditions. The SOC trajectory, also depicted in Fig. 7 (b), indirectly reflects the output power of fuel cell regulated by the selected rules. We can find that the SOC varies between 0.45 and 0.75 and finally converges to 0.63. As can be observed from Fig. 7 (c), the selected rules change obviously, and a common phenomenon can be found that when the fuel cell power is larger, the rule number is lower; and vice versa. By incorporating Figs. 7 (b) and (c), we can conclude that the called rules control the fuel cell power smaller under the condition of larger SOC and less driving power demand, e.g. from 0 to 300 s. In addition, when SOC is lower and power demand is larger, e.g. from 400 s to 600 s, the system certainly demands larger power output of fuel cell to satisfy the driving requirement. Fig. 7 (d) expresses the priority variation of selected rules. As mentioned above, the calling sequence of rules needs to conform to the priority order. The algorithm will select the rules with the first priority; if the rules do not satisfy the current state, the next priority should be searched until the last priority; and if all the rules do not meet the calling condition, the default rule is activated. From Fig. 7 (d), the invoked rule is switched among those with different priorities. To further validate reasonability of the proposed strategy, the power distribution is discussed in this study. The fuel cell output power distribution based on PMP and the rule learning strategy are compared in Figs. 7 (e) and Fig. 7 (f), respectively. As can be observed, the fuel cell distribution of both strategies looks similar. In the LA92 cycle, the average power demand is relatively is low, consequently the fuel cell power is mainly concentrated in the low power region, and the fuel cell power based on the offline PMP strategy verifies it, where the ratio of less than 6 kW reaches 68.11%, and the ratio of that based on the proposed method is 67.5%. Additionally, the driving cycle contains the high power demand partially, thus the higher fuel cell output region based on the proposed algorithm exists to meet the driving requirement. In short, the simulation results suggest that the proposed strategy can allocate the fuel cell power reasonably. Moreover, it is further validated that the rules learned by the algorithm do not raise over-fitting due to power distribution difference between PMP and rule learning.

Fig. 7. The LA92 driving cycle. (a) The fuel cell system efficiency; (b) The speed and SOC trajectories; (c) The selected rules and the corresponding fuel cell output power; (d) The rule priority; (e) The fuel cell power distribution based on PMP strategy; (f) The fuel cell power distribution based on rule learning strategy.

Fig. 8 details the simulation results based on HWFET cycle. As can be observed, HWFET belongs to the high speed driving cycle, of which the average power demand is relatively larger, therefore the battery is more actively engaged in driving the vehicle, and certainly the fuel cell output power also shifts towards the high efficiency region. That said, the proposed strategy is still effectively to reduce the hydrogen consumption and reasonably distribute the power under high speed driving conditions.

Fig. 8. The HWFET driving cycle simulation. (a) The speed and SOC trajectories; (b) The selected rules and the corresponding fuel cell output power; (c) The rule priority; (d) The fuel cell power distribution based on PMP strategy; (e) The fuel cell power distribution based on rule learning strategy.

B Blended Driving Cycle Simulation and Results Analysis

To further validate the performance of proposed strategy, a real driving cycle is simulated, of which the speed profile and corresponding results are shown in Fig. 9. The total trip duration and length is 2856 s and 26.07 km, respectively. It can be seen from Fig. 9 (b) that the actual driving cycle is mainly composed of the urban congested, slow driving and high speed driving conditions, fully reflecting the real driving environment. The SOC trajectory based on the problem algorithm is also shown in Fig. 9 (b). The driving power demand is depicted in Fig. 9 (c), demonstrating a relatively large variation range of power requirement; and Fig. 9 (d) describes the implementation sequences of selected rules responding to the current driving condition. By combining Figs. 9 (a) and (d), it can be found the rules belonging to first priority are mostly activated, and the

fuel cell power is relatively lower, rather than zero, when the power demand is low and the SOC is high (e.g., from 0 s to 1200 s), indicating that the proposed strategy will regulate more power output of the battery to alleviate the power burden imposed on the fuel cell and simultaneously avoid frequent start and stop. In this manner, the fuel cell lifetime can be potentially prolonged. The distribution of power demand in actual driving conditions is shown in Fig. 9 (e), and it varies within a large range, basically covering the road power requirements of different driving conditions. Fig. 9 (f) depicts the power distribution of fuel cell based on the offline PMP strategy. The fuel cell output power mainly locates in the low consumption area and slightly shifts towards the high efficiency area. The distribution of fuel cell power based on the rule learning strategy exhibits the similar profile, and more power output belongs to the high efficiency region, which reaches 33.57%, compared with that based on the PMP strategy, as shown in Fig. 9 (g). Nonetheless, more fuel cell power appears in the high-efficiency region, highlighting the effectiveness of proposed strategy.

To intuitively verify the effectiveness of the proposed strategy, the traditional thermostat control strategy, based on which the fuel cell only works in high efficiency area, is also applied to evaluate the performance with presented strategy, and the related results are shown in Table VIII. As can be found, the final hydrogen consumption incurred by the proposed strategy increases by 4.25%, compared with the total hydrogen consumption based on PMP; and yet declines by 16.51% in comparison with that based on the conventional deterministic rules. Thus, the savings manifest that the proposed strategy can attain the anticipated fuel performance in real driving conditions. It can also be seen from Table VIII that the average time consumption in each step based on the three strategies is 0.00488 s, 0.000304 s and 0.000539 s, on a desktop computer with the CPU of an i5 core and the memory of 16 gigabytes. Obviously, the calculation intensity is acceptable, highlighting the feasibility of online application. However, when applying the PMP strategy to realize the optimal energy management, the equivalent coefficient strongly correlates to the driving cycle, and needs to know the driving condition in advance. By the contrary, the rule learning strategy does not need to acquire the driving information ahead of departure and enables determination of the output power of fuel cell only according to the current driving condition. To conclude, the strategy proposed in this study can properly allocate the fuel cell power with fast calculation speed to attain the improved fuel economy, and meanwhile be immune from the driving knowledge, manifesting its online application potential.

Fig. 9. The real driving cycle simulation. (a) The landing satellite image; (b) The speed and SOC trajectories; (c) The load required power; (d) The SOC trajectories; (e) The road power demand; (f) The distribution based on PMP; (g) The distribution based on rule learning.

Table VIII Simulation results of PMP and Rule Learning Strategies

	PMP-based	Deterministic rule-based	Rule Learning-based
Hydrogen consumption during driving	142.82	166.26	152.91
SOC deviation	-0.0024	-0.0595	+0.0234
Equivalent hydrogen consumption (g)	-0.54	-13.68	3.18
Total hydrogen consumption (g)	143.36 (+4.25%)	179.33 (-16.51%)	149.73
Ratio fuel economy	1	1.25	1.04
Calculate time (s)	13.9433	0.8688	1.5395

Note: +: Increment; -: Decrement

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This study investigates the rule learning based EMS to improve the energy consumption economy of FCHEVs. Firstly, the PMP is employed to solve the offline optimal allocation of fuel cell power and plan the SOC trajectory of battery. Then, the improved RIPPER algorithm is employed to successfully excavate a total of 21 rules from the solved optimization results with the inputs of vehicle speed, acceleration and battery SOC and the outputs of fuel cell power. The multiple linear regression algorithm is applied to fit the parameters of each rule set. Simulation results reveal that the proposed rule learning strategy can achieve more than 95% savings of energy consumption economy for FCHEVs, compared with the offline PMP based optimal EMSs. Furthermore, the proposed strategy shows online implementation potential owing to its low computation intensity and independence on prior driving knowledge.

The rule set in this paper cannot cover all driving conditions, and hence it is imperative to continuously update and correct the rule parameters according to the actual driving environment as time goes on. This is certainly our future research focus. Besides, the fuel cell static model applied in this study neglects the dynamic performance. How to establish a more reasonable EMS based on rule learning with consideration of the dynamic performance of fuel cell needs to be further investigated. Furthermore, the cost of hydrogen production may vary with different regions and seasons. How to properly consider the influence arisen by the price of hydrogen in the target function and optimize the overall operating cost also needs to be researched.

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